

DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION OF CLASSICAL POETIC DISCOURSE: IN THE CONTEXT OF BAKHTIYAR VAHABZADEH'S WORK

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Abstract

Literature is a field that reflects life through images and is directly related to the period in which it was created. Philosophical thoughts and trends are also influential factors in the creation of literary material. Rules polished over time, forms accepted as standards acquire classical value. The work of Bakhtiyar Vahabzadeh, a prominent representative of Azerbaijani literature who lived and created in the 20th century, philosopher, poet, playwright, combines classical tradition and literary heritage. Respecting the creativity and tradition of the classics of world and Azerbaijani literature, Bakhtiyar Vahabzadeh demonstrated a classical approach to the literary texts he created, thus keeping the literary heritage alive in modern literature. This is the integration and interpretation of the classics into the new era. New digital technologies also bring new methods and ways to the expression and dissemination of literature.

It is understood from the research that the digital transformation of literature is viewed as a process of change in terms of structure, meaning, and function. In this context, Bakhtiyar Vahabzadeh's work is analyzed as a poetic expression of various transitions, and these features are shown to emerge in a new way in the digital environment. In the empirical part, social media comments were analyzed and it was determined that readers often share the poet's verses as a commentary, evaluating him as a representative of classical literature, that is, the reader is no longer passive, but actively participates in the interpretation of the text, supports its digitization, and wishes it to be accessible. As a result, it can be said that classical poetry gains a new life in the digital environment: it becomes not just a readable text, but a part of everyday communication. In this regard, Bakhtiyar Vahabzadeh's work acts as both a literary heritage and a dynamic poetic model living in modern digital culture.

Keywords: Classical poetic discourse, tradition, heritage, digitalization, transformation.

Introduction

In scientific literature, there are unique and different definitions and meanings of classicism. Against the background of this diversity, the unambiguous criterion of classicism is its value, a style that has passed the test of time and retained its human relevance. The official online encyclopedia website of the famous "Encyclopaedia Britannica" describes classical literature as follows: "Classical literature, the literature of ancient Greece and Rome (see Greek literature; Latin literature). The term, usually spelled "classical," is also used for the literature of any language in a period notable for the excellence and enduring quality of its writers' works. In ancient Greece such a period extended from about 500 to 320 bce. The Golden Age of Rome ran from about 70 bce to 18 ce. French literature of the second half of the 17th century is considered classical, as is English literature of 1660–1714. The works produced and the critical standards that prevailed in both eras emulated those of the Classical periods in Greek and Latin, although this criterion is not an essential characteristic of a classical literature." [7]

As can be seen, classics are important not only for a single nation, but for humanity as a whole. It is as if classical traditions play the role of a base, a foundation for literary genre and approach. We also learn from the article "Who is a Classic?" by the French writer and critic Charles Saint-Beau (1804-1869), the founder of the biographical school in literary criticism, that the concept of Classic is historically variable and has acquired different meanings in different periods. The term

first emerged as a concept related to the upper class in ancient Rome, and was later applied to literature. Previously, only ancient (Greek and Roman) authors were considered classics, but over time, as national literatures were formed (Italian, French, etc.), their classics also began to appear. Although academic definitions mainly present a classic as a "regular, exemplary writer", this approach is limited. A true classic is a writer who enriches the human spirit, discovers universal truths, remains relevant regardless of time, and creates a personal yet universally understandable style.

The goal of the word masters who created examples of classical literature was not to make a revolution at all, but rather to create harmony and balance. However, there is a subtle line here, which is that reaching excessive regularity is also unimportant.

In classical theory, the superiority of cognition (reason) over imagination and feeling has long been accepted. This approach has been dominant in Latin and especially French literature. However, in large-scale literary examples (for example, in epics and dramas), passion and emotion play a stronger role than cognition. It should be noted that cognition also dominates in the work and philosophical thought of Bakhtiyar Vahabzadeh, a prominent representative of Azerbaijani literature. According to Buffon's approach, the idea, structure and execution in a classical work should be in unity, the work should not be fragmented, and should be built on a single plan. Goethe also considered the classics alive, healthy, and strong, compared to romanticism, its unit of measurement is not time, but quality.

In general, if we look at the classics from the perspective of broad literary criticism, the classics cannot be evaluated with uniform standards, and the systematic thinking here is a product of later periods. In the modern era, the main point in looking at the classics is that the greatest geniuses are often not initially accepted, but are re-evaluated over time. And this assessment often changes depending on the historical context.

Charles Saint-Beau (1804-1869) in his article "Who is a Classic?" notes that the concept of classic is a category that must be both preserved and expanded. It is impossible to become a classic by imitating only the purity of language and the elegance of style; such an approach produces artificial results and distances itself from true creativity. "The value of the classics lies in their power to express universal human experience. From this point of view, classical literature should not be limited to the boundaries of a particular people or era. On the contrary, it should be imagined as a vast "temple" encompassing various cultures and literary traditions. Within this temple, great representatives of both Western and Eastern literature – geniuses who lived in different times and in different circumstances – come together. Such an approach allows us to understand literature as a global and timeless phenomenon and shows that great works of art establish a "dialogue" with each other, transcending peoples and centuries." [6]

Thus, the concept of classicism is an expression of aesthetic and moral values that have stood the test of time. On the one hand, it is universal, on the other hand, it has an individual character and is rediscovered by each reader. Classical works not only enrich a person aesthetically, but also have a power that reconciles him with himself and the world, creating lasting moral stability. Ali Nazim wrote: "When the classical heritage, tradition is viewed as a passed stage, an outdated era, many discoveries of generations before us remain forgotten, and these discoveries become problems that are much more difficult for future generations to understand and explain."

"The trends that emerged in the West at the beginning of the 20th century emerged from the need to destroy classical molds, from certain economic, political and social conditions, from the inner restlessness of man, from the desire to freely express himself, to change the world, from a revanchist mood against the past and traditionalism. For example, expressionism, which emerged in the first decade of the 20th century, was an expression of a reaction to capitalism and the political situation of that time." [2, 37]

The trends that emerged in the West at the beginning of the 20th century were attempts to destroy classical molds, to escape from certain economic, political and social realities, human suffering, to change the world, to speak out against the past and traditionalism. However, since the classics have already passed certain tests, they have maintained their relevance at all times, both in world literature in general and in the literature of individual nations, as well as in Azerbaijani literature. Because Man stands at the center of these literary examples. "In ancient Egyptian and Greek literature, in many examples of classical literature, in Nizami Ganjavi's "Khamasa", Rumi's "Masnavi", in Nasimi's

and Fuzuli's ghazals, in the poems of Sabir, Javid, Hadi, man was presented as a supreme value, and the idea of the unity of the world was instilled as a fundamental principle." [2, 167]

Although there have been tendencies to oppose the classics at different times, over time, ideas improve, and a return to them takes place. The attitude towards the classics and the literary heritage they created can receive its true value, so that the essence and essence of their creativity can be fully understood, and the objective-historical picture of the times they lived in, as well as the national-spiritual and moral realities, are not left out of context. Let's give it to N. Jabbarli: "In my opinion, when analyzing the creativity of postmodernists, we should talk about an approach to reality rather than reality. Because both classical literature and contemporary literature (meaning those written in traditional forms) are engaged in reflecting reality. It's just that the attitudes of postmodernists and representatives of the new generation who want to be called (and also become) postmodernists towards reality are different. More precisely, they are crude and naked. Their biggest flaw is to bring their chaotic attitudes towards society and the world, their hatred and hatred to their creativity." [3, 52]

For a long time, classical poetry was perceived as operating with an unchanging, stable and closed system of rules, but it is not static, but a dynamic system. The concept of classicism is reinterpreted at all times, changing and expanding against the background of new aesthetic criteria and literary experiments and approaches. In this regard, classical poetics is not just a frozen model of the past, but a living structure that is transformed over time, developing in interaction with various literary movements. The dynamism of classical poetics is also manifested in its dialogue with various literary traditions. The process of continuous interaction between antiquity, the Middle Ages, the Renaissance and modern literature enriches the concept of classicism. As a result of this process, classical poetics can act not only as a set of certain rules, but also as an open system that stimulates new creative possibilities.

Classical poetic discourse is a style, an aesthetic and intellectual system, formed in classical literature and poetry, which, despite being repeated for centuries, can always acquire new meanings, and has a certain set of aesthetics, structure and ideas. The features of classical poetic discourse have been formed and attracted attention in different periods. According to Aristotle, order and integrity are the main features, and events, images and ideas within the work are harmoniously and purposefully interconnected. According to Mikhail Bakhtin, dialogical and multilayered meaning is important in classical poetic discourse, the text is enriched by the interaction of different voices and views. Yuri Lotman notes that the codified structure of the classical poetic style works through certain symbols, forms and aesthetic principles; it is an open system associated with cultural memory. However, the most important thing is that the seemingly rigid rules of poetic discourse are dynamic and adapt to all times.

Tradition and heritage in the work of Bakhtiyar Vahabzadeh

The poet, playwright, writer, and publicist Bakhtiyar Vahabzadeh, who played a very important role in the poetic and literary heritage of 20th century Azerbaijan, is one of the artists who kept the classical tradition alive throughout his entire work. Bakhtiyar Vahabzadeh was born on August 16, 1925 in the city of Sheki. After receiving his secondary education here, he entered the Faculty of Philology of Baku State University and graduated from it in 1947. From the same year, he began his scientific and pedagogical activity at the university and taught the history of Azerbaijani literature for many years. His creativity began with poetry from an early age. His first poems were published in the 1940s, but he became known to a wide readership with the poem "Gulustan". This work was subjected to serious criticism during the Soviet period because it reflected the ideas of national liberation, and the author faced certain pressures. Bakhtiyar Vahabzadeh is the author of poems with both lyrical and socio-political content. Homeland, freedom, language, national identity and human morality are the main themes in his work. The poet's works such as "Latin language", "Mother language" were widely distributed and highly appreciated. He also worked as a playwright and wrote a number of plays. ("Shabi Hijran", "Faryad", "Gallows", "Mugham" and others) He was not only a poet, but also a literary scholar. He conducted research on the creativity of Azerbaijani classics and wrote scientific works. He worked as a professor at the university for many years, playing an important role in the upbringing of many students. Bakhtiyar Vahabzadeh was also distinguished for his social and political activities. He was a deputy of the Milli Majlis of the Republic of Azerbaijan and actively participated in the promotion of the ideas of independence. He was awarded high honorary titles as an Honored Scientist and People's Poet. His work remains relevant today as a continuation of the national spirit, the idea of freedom and the classical poetic tradition in Azerbaijani literature.

"The relationship between predecessor and successor in literature is always relevant. Today, it is rising above the past and tradition. Understanding, feeling, and learning the predecessor is the conscientious duty and respect of the successor. In the work of Bakhtiyar Vahabzadeh, the philosophical master of words of modern Azerbaijani literature, honoring his predecessors, drawing inspiration from the masters, and reviving them as an image are among the most striking aspects." [5, 1219]

One of the most important directions in Bakhtiyar Vahabzadeh's creativity is a specific attitude towards the classics, drawing on them and, where appropriate, criticism. However, this attitude does not remain only in the scope of a national attitude, but also has a more general and human character, since it raises the problem of Man. Here, not only the position of a nation, but also the necessary points for humanity in general come to the fore. In this regard, Chingiz Aitmatov's ideas are valuable: "Vahabzadeh's poetic thinking is national in nature. This is an exceptionally necessary condition, if you are able to be an active part of the speech of the people of which you are a child, if you are able to make your contribution to the living language architecture of your people. At the same time, Vahabzadeh's culture of

poetic thinking acquires a superior essence and rises from national to universal. In this case, when you read an Azerbaijani poet, you read the world" [1] In this sense, it is necessary to understand the work of Bakhtiyar Vahabzade as a translation and interpretation of classical poetry into the modern world. Although love for the homeland and nation is the main direction in Vahabzade's work. However, this direction in no way surpasses universal love and values, from this point of view, it is even possible to call him a cosmopolitan, a citizen of the world.

B. Vahabzadeh, both in his artistic creativity and in his scientific works, was sympathetic to the classical tradition and derived from them. The poet, who repeatedly mentions the traditions of Azerbaijani folklore, prominent representatives of classical poetry - Khagani, Nizami, Fuzuli, Nasimi, Sabir, Mirza Jalil Mammadguluzadeh and others, brings historical heroes and music, which have a position in history and the development of national consciousness, into modern discourse as part of the classical heritage, presents and analyzes them in a modern approach. In Vahabzadeh's philosophical thought, the experience filtered from ancient times and the modern approach form a unity. Feeding on predecessors and drawing on folk literature examples form the basis of his poetic philosophy. However, this is not a transfer, but a striving for innovation by giving an individual-human approach to the essence. Human cognition forms a specific approach to concepts from the moment it begins to perceive life and the world. This understanding in many cases has an individual, individual-psychological, ethnopsychological and human character. Although human, individual, individual-psychological approaches create a separate impression in themselves, they are also related to ethnopsychology in their essence. The attitude towards opposites arises from their functionality and situational reaction. The loading of spiritual content on perceived concepts both distinguishes peoples and ethnic groups from each other and connects them to each other. In this sense, in Bakhtiyar's work, the classical and classicized literary and historical heritage is also presented with archetypes.

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The main archetypes of classical literature can also be seen in the work of B. Vahabzadeh. The hero archetype (Babek in Vahabzadeh's play "The Gallows Tree", Gur Shad in the play "The Sword That Cuts Us" or "The Goyturks") attracts attention as an image that overcomes difficulties and goes through trials in epic epics and tragedies. Also, the wise old man or teacher archetype, as an image that gives knowledge and direction, is important in the interpretation of real-historical personalities, literary figures and archetypes of the classical tradition in modern literature, as in the image of Sabir in the poem "Aghlar Guleghan" dedicated to poet Mirza Alakbar Sabir, the image of poet Sahhat, the image of poet Muhammad in the poem "Shabi-hijan" dedicated to Fuzuli, and the image of Dede Gorgud, who is often mentioned in his poems. The traitor or enemy archetype, which is one of the most important archetypes of classical literature, is a common issue in the literature of all peoples of the world as a force that creates conflict. The most important nuance of the struggle is revealed in the collision created with the images of the enemy. In this sense, the same motifs and archetypes are given place in the work of Bakhtiyar Vahabzadeh.

Starting from ancient literature, the archetype of the road is one of the traditional motifs considered to be eternal in the literature of the medieval world and classical East. The archetype of the road is not only about the distance covered physically. The inner world, spiritual development, and mental activity of the character are also important here. Along with the dynamics of the plot of the created heroes, the crises in their inner world, contradictory thoughts, and spiritual states arising from the unity of opposites lead them to spiritual development, in other words, a journey into oneself, into oneself, which leads to progressive changes in the heroes, or natural defeat. In Vahabzadeh's work, heroes and characters corresponding to this archetype are also created in most of the characters. In this sense, the characters of Qara Khagan and Dulu Khan in his play "The Sword That Cuts Us" or "The Goyturks" are interesting. The changes that occur in their thinking over time bring both Qara Khagan and Dulu Khan to truth and justice. However, here the spiritual journey manifests itself differently in both characters. "The Black Khagan's understanding of the truth comes late, it is already too late for

everything, his possession of the Great Turk blood reveals his pride, he stains the sword he owns with his own blood. The fact that the Black Khagan takes his punishment with his own hands is perceived as his return to the right path, dramaturgically the event does not reach the level of tragedy; he is not killed by the main character. We see the same motif with Dulu Khan. He also learns from his mistakes, wants to kill himself with the sword he took without worthiness, those who forgive and understand him prevent this murder. This can also be characterized as a kind of purification. Dulu Khan is also a character in development, with this the author expresses the possibility of learning from mistakes, that genetic memory speaks sooner or later." [5,490]

Humanities and digitalization in the modern era

In the modern world, digitalization is observed in all fields as a result of the development of science and technology, and the humanities and literature are not left out of it. "As we look to the future, literature is no longer confined to printed pages but is evolving into dynamic, multimedia experiences, challenging both readers and writers to engage with stories in innovative ways. The future of literature will be more inclusive, interactive, and deeply integrated with technology." [4]

Technology has revolutionized the creation, writing, access, and interaction of written fiction. The widespread use of technology and e-books and audiobooks has made literature more accessible and engaging, enabling the interactive presentation of fiction on digital storytelling platforms. Digital tools allow authors to experiment with multimedia elements, combine text with audio, video, and interactive features that enhance the reading experience, and reach readers and listeners more quickly. The interdisciplinary nature of digital technologies also encourages collaboration between literary scholars, coders, and data analysts, enriching literary research with new perspectives and methodologies.

Digitization expands the collaboration between literary studies and technology in the humanities, creating new ways to understand texts through data visualization. As technology advances, the reality possibilities of literature expand, and e-books, audiobooks, and e-readers, etc., comfortably connect with their readers and listeners on various platforms.

The concept of transformation

In the era of digitalization, transformation has become one of the current concepts (Latin transformare - "to change its shape"), meaning that any system, object or concept changes not in form, but in essence, gaining a new quality. Now, the transformation and transformation of literature, like in other fields, is one of the priority points. Transformation in literature is realized in ways such as changing the form, genre and means of expression of the text, and restructuring classical poetic systems in a new context. That is, the forms do not just change, their delivery and function are also optimized, moving to another level.

Digital transformation in literature is the process of adapting classical poetic discourse to the digital environment, re-forming its structure, expanding its functionality and enriching new forms of expression. In this

process, the text is not only transferred from the physical book to the screen, but also the structure, perception and interpretation methods of the work change. Digital literature is also a data source, an object of analysis, and an opportunity for interactivity. While in the classical model of literature the reader is in a passive position, in literary works integrated into a digital platform the reader is active, able to play the role of a participant-partner, interpreter, and sometimes even co-author.

Integration of Bakhtiyar Vahabzadeh's legacy into a digital platform and a modern reader

Since Bakhtiyar Vahabzadeh's work combines classicism with modernism, tradition with modernity, past with future, heritage with innovation, its interpretation in the digital environment is also easily solved. Especially on social network accounts, platforms such as YouTube and Facebook, the reviews written about Vahabzadeh's life, activities, biography, and individual examples of his work generally comment on the modern reader's attitude to him from various angles despite the change in time. The reactions to Bakhtiyar Vahabzadeh's work on digital platforms show that the reader is no longer just a perceiver of the text, but also a subject actively participating in its interpretation. The comments posted on social media platforms prove that literary discourse has become democratized and individual experiences have become collective meaning.

When searching for the title "Bakhtiyar Vahabzadeh" on the YouTube platform, hundreds of short and multi-minute video materials come to the fore. These materials cover both his biography, creative examples, and the works he has performed. An analysis of the reader-viewer-listener-interpreter comments written on these types of posts shows that reader reactions are mainly emotional, national-identical, and literary-aesthetic in nature.

In the era of the reconstruction of classical poetic discourse in the digital environment by the reader-interpreter, we observe that on platforms, the poet, who is considered a poet of the people, a truth-seeker, a great son of the Turkic world, and a source of pride, is also considered a spiritual continuation of classical literature in the modern era, on a par with artists such as Nizami and Fuzuli: "In my opinion, there is no step behind Nizami and Fuzuli. Nizami, Fuzuli, and Bekhtiyar Vahabzade are also great artists and poets of this people..." or "You will live just as the Nizamis and Nasimis lived, poet, be sure of that...", etc.

In a significant part of the comments, the poet is presented and analyzed as a philosopher, and sometimes he is called "the second philosopher poet of Azerbaijan after Nasimi." These kinds of thoughts can be seen more in the comments written on the video material of his philosophical poems. The digital reader also evaluates Vahabzadeh's work, which has mastered ancient Eastern and mystical philosophy, not only in an aesthetic, but also in a philosophical-spiritual context when expressing opinions. In reader reactions, the author is idealized by associating it with concepts such as "truth", "sect" and "culture", which shows that he is presented as a spiritual authority in the digital environment. That is, the reader-listener does not just accept information ready-made, but also gives it meaning and turns the author into an ideological symbol. The reader

is able to apply a psychological and philosophical approach to the text, the digital reader is already a subject of analytical interpretation. Analysis of social media comments shows that Bakhtiyar Vahabzadeh's work is perceived in the digital environment not only on an emotional, but also on a philosophical and analytical level. Readers interpret the socio-political and spiritual problems in the author's works in the context of the conflict of emotion and rationality, and at the same time present him as one of the top figures of the national literary canon. This approach shows that classical poetic discourse is becoming relevant again in the digital environment and is being adopted by the younger generation. This shows that the digital reader does not approach the issue only from an emotional aspect, but also understands, analyzes and relates to the literary text.

It is also interesting that the reader, moved by the video material, quotes the poem that left a mark on his memory and impressed him with Bakhtiyar Vahabzadeh's work. This shows that classical poetic texts function not only as aesthetic objects in the digital environment, but also as active communicative tools. The fact that readers use the poet's verses to express their emotional and spiritual states demonstrates that these texts are fixed in the collective memory and have become an integral part of everyday digital discourse. On the platforms, comments such as "Where there is no one else but oneself, a person forgets that he is a human being..." and "What a beautiful line: "...if you have a confidant who knows your troubles..." originated from Bakhtiyar Vahabzadeh's own work.

We would like to emphasize in particular that the social media comments used in the study were analyzed as empirical material, in accordance with ethical principles, the users' data were anonymized, names were not given, and specific links were not provided. The comments were taken on a purposeful basis, and only reactions related to the text and carrying content were included in the study.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it is worth noting that the study shows that digital transformation in literature, along with technological advances, leads to a structural and functional restructuring of classical poetic discourse. The study of Bakhtiyar Vahabzadeh's work shows that literary texts in the digital domain play active communicative and interpretive roles, rather than remaining passive objects of perception. Empirical studies conducted on social media comments show that readers not only read classical poetry, but also repeat it, expressing their spiritual and emotional states through the poet's poems. This shows that the text has become an important component of digital discourse and is strengthened as a component of collective memory.

The study shows that digital transformation in literature, along with technological advances, leads to a structural and functional restructuring of classical poetic discourse. The study of Bakhtiyar Vahabzadeh's work shows that literary texts in the digital domain play active communicative and interpretive roles, rather than remaining passive objects of perception. Empirical studies of social media commentary show that readers not only read classical poetry, but also retell it, expressing their own spiritual and emotional states through the

poet's poems. This suggests that text has become an important component of digital discourse and is becoming entrenched as a component of collective memory.

Digital technological development does not move away from the classics, classical literature and those who keep it alive use innovative opportunities to "simplify" and make classical discourse accessible, allowing it to spread more widely and gain new life in the digital environment.

Vahabzadeh's work acts not only as a classical poetic system, but also as a dynamic poetic model that provides a transition between various historical and cultural stages. When Bakhtiyar Vahabzadeh's work is analyzed from the perspective of "transitional poetics", it becomes clear that his poetic system reflects various transformation processes on the historical, psychological and aesthetic levels. These processes acquire a different content in the digital environment and ultimately lead to the transformation of classical poetic discourse into an interactive and communicative form.

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